

The Role of Personality Characteristics and Psychological Harassment Behaviors Which Employees Are Exposed on Work Alienation

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Abstract—The main purpose of the research is to address the role of psychological harassment behaviors (mobbing) to which employees are exposed and personality characteristics over work alienation. Research population was composed of the employees of Provincial Special Administration. A survey with four sections was created to measure variables and reach out the basic goals of the research. Correlation and step-wise regression analyses were performed to investigate the separate and overall effects of sub-dimensions of psychological harassment behaviors and personality characteristic on work alienation of employees. Correlation analysis revealed significant but weak relationships between work alienation and psychological harassment and personality characteristics. Step-wise regression analysis revealed also significant relationships between work alienation variable and assault to personality, direct negative behaviors (sub dimensions of mobbing) and openness (sub-dimension of personality characteristics). Each variable was introduced into the model step by step to investigate the effects of significant variables in explaining the variations in work alienation. While the explanation ratio of the first model was 13%, the last model including three variables had an explanation ratio of 24%.

Keywords—Alienation, Five-Factor Personality Characteristics, Mobbing, Psychological Harassment, Work Alienation.

I. INTRODUCTION

THERE are some issues for organizations which have not been sufficiently emphasized or mentioned about. Privacy, complexity and not coming to light of these issues have retarded the sufficient emphasize of such issues. Psychological harassment, in other words mobbing, have already existed in several organizations but it hasn't been come to light, disregarded for several reasons and it has been still considered as a complex issue not directly observed from outside [1].

Mobbing is a comprehensive and complex issue than can negatively influence the work relations and health of employees of public and private organizations decrease the performance of both organizations and employees and cannot be explained with a single reason. Psychological harassment (mobbing) is an organizational problem arisen through the

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interactions among personal characteristics, position of the sufferer, organizational and socio-economic conditions [2]. Today, although mobbing is a common phenomenon in several countries, it is generally envisaged as a taboo and researchers mostly avoided working over the issue [3].

Similar to mobbing, alienation has also become a social and psychological problem among today's individuals. Although alienation is an old issue as much as human history, work alienation of an employee is a new concept to be emphasized. Work alienation will alienate the individual from his organization and colleagues and consequently will make the individual spending most of his life with colleagues unhappy. Organizations should be aware of dissatisfaction, concerns, complains and corresponding hostile behaviors and actions (like mobbing) of their employees and should intervene such actions before the situation became graver.

The present study was conducted to investigate the relationships between mobbing subjected by employees of public organizations and world alienation and to address the role of personal characteristics in these relationships. Although a similar study was not come across in literature, there are some studies investigating and measuring these three parameters separately.

II. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

A. Psychological Harassment (Mobbing)

Today, mobbing has become a widespread organization risk space. Recent researches on mobbing were all about to understand mobbing and distinguish it from harmless rudeness, scornfulness and similar nettlesome personal attitude and behaviors [4]. Together with discussing and investigating the issue in scientific works, penal sanctions started to be implemented against mobbing indicators [5].

Mobbing is continuous and repeated behaviors against an individual by a together action of a group of co-workers through spending disrespectful words, criticizing, gossiping and dispensing false information to isolate the targeted individual from social relations, continuous jeering about the targeted individual [6]. Mobbing is an organizational safety and health problem [7] and includes repeated and continuous attempts to wear away, prohibit and oppress someone or to get reactions from someone. For an action to be a mobbing, it should continuously provoke, fear or force or discomfort the targeted individual. The individual experiencing serious traumas and even losing their jobs through mobbing are called

as “victims” and the ones able to overcome the mobbing actions are called as “sufferer” [8].

Mobbing is an emotional assault and is an action of someone to create an aggressive atmosphere to force individuals to fire from their jobs either with or without their consents through malignant and jeering actions to reduce the social prestige of the targeted ones [9].

According to Björkvist et al. (1994) calling mobbing as harassment at work place, this concept was defined as the repeated behaviors performed against one or more individuals who are not able to defend themselves for any reasons to harm them either emotionally or sometimes physically [10].

Tim Field defines physiological harassment as a continuous and relentless assault against the trust and self-respect of “mobbing” sufferers. According to such a definition, it can be seen as the *effort to die-off the self-esteem of the victim*. The basic reason underlying such a behavior is the desire of subordination, subjection and eradication [11].

Swedish researchers Heinz Leymann, defining evil behaviors and attitudes realized in several ways in organizations as mobbing, is the leading researcher defining harassment concept in work life [4]. According to Leymann, mobbing is a terror and a systematic process applied through hostile unethical methods by one or more individuals against the targeted individual. With mobbing, the individual is discarded in a defenseless and desperate fashion [12], [13].

Since psychological harassment (mobbing) is a new concept, there hasn't been a common international term for the concept. For instance, while the term “bullying” is used in Norway, Japan and Anglo-Saxon countries, the term “moral harassment” is commonly used in France [14]. The term “mobbing” is used in other European countries [15].

The concept of mobbing (psychological harassment) is derived from the English word “mob” meaning to gather at a place, assault and annoy [15], [16]. The term mobbing (psychological harassment) was used for the first time by Konrad Lorenz (1963, 1965, 1968) to define the animal behaviors. At the same times, Swedish doctor Peter-Paul Heinemann (1972) used the term “mobbing” (psychological harassment) to define the aggressive behaviors of students of school against each other [17].

Psychological harassment is described with different definitions based on cultural, social environment and specific conditions. Bullying, aggression, patronage and suppression are among those terms used to define the assaults or to characterize the individual exposed to assaults. However, it is difficult to clearly explain the difference between these concepts. While some of them have the same meanings, some others indicate different cases [14]. Leymann defined 45 different psychological harassment behaviors and then classified these behaviors under five different categories. These are [13]; 1. *The assaults preventing an individual to express oneself* (continuous interruption, continuous criticism of the thing done by an individual and etc.), 2. *The assaults to social relationships* (not to talk by surrounding people, not to provide a separate work space and etc.), 3. *The assaults to social prestige of an individual* (make a mockery of someone,

spending evil words behind someone and etc.), 4. *The assaults to work and life quality of someone* (assigning meaningless tasks, continuous replacement of works and etc.), 5. *The assaults directly influencing the health of someone* (threat through physical violence, direct sexual assaults and etc.).

Psychological harassment is different from maltreating of the managers. In maltreating, managers use their power to trample over the others, get over the limits of respect in small unfavorable conditions, contempt and exhibit insulting behaviors. In this case, it is really hard to distinguish the behaviors. The only difference between maltreating and psychological harassment is the fact that maltreating is not a general behavior; it doesn't have confidential and manipulative characteristics [18]. There isn't much difference between a normal conflict and psychological harassment. The basic difference between them is the continuity and repeated fashion of psychological harassment [19]. Every negative behavior exposed by an individual in a work place should not be considered as psychological harassment. The behavior should include some elements to mention about a psychological harassment. These elements are [1];

- It should realize in a work place.
- It can occur between a superior and sub-ordinate, can be applied by sub-ordinated to superiors or be realized between equal orders.
- It should be made systematically.
- It should be in a continuous fashion.
- It should be intentional.
- It should aim intimidation, passivation and removal from the job.
- It should harm the professional status or health of the sufferer.
- The unfavorable attitudes and behaviors may be confidential or open.

Every individual exposed to psychological harassment is not sufferer. In general, it is possible to mentioned about three types of sufferers: *real sufferers, the ones perceiving the suffer as exaggerated, the ones using the suffer for strategic purposes*. *Real sufferers*, are the individuals who are fragile, non-assertive, not able to say no or not able to manage the conflict in which he got into and antagonizing the case. They are usually the victims of force breach of managers or the malignant co-workers. They are easily exploited. *In the second group individuals*, there is a perceptual disorder. They can perceive a pressure or authoritarian behavior in work place as harassment. These individuals envisage themselves at the center of the universe and perceive the outer world as a threat. *The third group individuals* are so-called victims. They exaggerate the case they exposed to and try to reach their goals strategically. Although they complain about the case, they don't suffer and get along with their lives in a comfortable fashion. They know about the legislations and inter-organizational rights they have and orient the people around [18].

Psychological harassment is way above work-stress [18]. According to Salmivalli et al. (1996), there are six factors in a

psychological harassment [20]; 1. **Bully:** The active, orienting individual exhibiting leadership behaviors. 2. **Assistant:** The active individual assisting the bully. 3. **Enhancer:** The individual encouraging and monitoring the bully. 4. **Defender:** The individual defending and consoling the victim. 5. **Outsider:** The individual not interested in actions and staying outside the process. 6. **Victim:** The individual passive throughout the process, not able to defend himself or don't know how to defend.

There is a power imbalance between the parties of psychological harassment. The victim thinks that he/she could not defend himself in the case [21]. Mobbing actions in an organizational structure may realize in horizontal or vertical fashions. Vertical mobbing is not limited with a mobbing directed from upper management to sub-ordinate levels. It may be bidirectional, either from up to down or from down to up. Horizontal mobbing is observed among the individuals with equal status. It is a type of mobbing existing among the individuals with functional relationships with each other [11].

Psychological intimidation results in negative outcomes in health, psychologies and financial status of individuals directly exposed to such behaviors or witnessed such behaviors [22]. Possible outcomes may be weakness, loss of power, chronic fatigue, various pains and aches-like physical disorders, hostile feeling, loss of memory, hypersensitivity, aggressive feelings, anger, staying away from social relations-like psychological syndromes [23].

B. Work Alienation

Although alienation came into prominence in the first works of Marx (1844/1932), the concept was referenced in a broad spectrum of subject covering philosophy, sociology, psychology and [24]. The concept of alienation mentioned in various disciplines was defined with the same meaning in essence, but with minor differences in detail [25].

Hegel was the first who used the concept of alienation. Hegel (1991) supports that alienation resulted from the differentiation between physical and emotional existence of an individual. Hegel used the concept of alienation as the remise from independent existence through blockade of 'self' and even secession form personality [26].

Alienation usually results from orientation both to himself and to nature to make sense of his existence and it is a concept either increasing the awareness of an individual or indicating the distance of an individual from himself or surroundings [27]. According to Blauner (1964), alienation is the thought of separation in minds and lives of individuals blocking the integrity of alienation experiences and activities [28]. According to Marx (1975), alienation is a process spoiling the natural operation of daily life of an individual. With alienation, natural integrity of an individual is spoiled up and the individual is then separated as an "employee" and an "individual" [29]. The most commonly accepted definitions for alienation in literature are provided in the following Table I;

TABLE I
 DEFINITION & DESCRIPTION OF ALIENATION [30]

Fromm (1955)	The feeling of an individual as an alien or alienated to himself.
Seeman (1959,1975)	Definition with regard to weakness, meaningless, irregularity, social isolation and alienation to himself.
Horowitz (1966)	Excessive differentiation firstly from the objects of the world, secondly from the humans, thirdly from the opinions of the people.
Schacht (1970)	The case in which the individual keeps himself separated from the other elements surrounding him.
Miller (1975)	Isolation from the others in an objective fashion.
Kanungo (1979)	Since working is perceived as the potential deficiency to meet the specific needs and expectations, the generalized cognitive (or belief) state of psychological alienation from the work.
Hircfeld & Feild (2000)	The reflection of an individual as irrelevant or independent from the professional world.

When the alienation is defined with regard to work alienation, the definition can be explained in a more concrete fashion. Hoy, Blazovsky and Newland (1983) indicated work alienation as the reflection of disappointment feelings experienced by an individual about his employment status in an organization [31].

Work alienation in brief is the weakness feeling of an individual against the work done by him. Such a feeling results from the fears of the individual and significantly affects the works and consequently the individual starts to lose the control over himself and his work [32]. According to Aiken and Hage [33] work alienation is the negative feelings resulted from moving away from career targets of an individual and in compliance with the professional norms. Among the reasons of alienation, individual's inability to express himself through his works, in compliance with the realities of the work, excessive emotional disaffection from his work, secession and alienation from his work can be counted. Emotional work alienation may force the employee to perform the emotional behavioral rules expected from him. Consequently, employee will experience increasing work alienation [26].

Marx indicates that alienation at work place existed as a result of some conditions. These conditions are; *a) inability of the employee to create ties with both the product he produced and the production tools, b) not to know fully about the supports he provided to production process and roles he played in this process, c) inability of the employee to adapt the work processes controlled by unordinary power or state and d) separation of work tasks into relatively small pieces and allowing the employee to use his intelligence and abilities in a very limited fashion* [34].

There are some characteristics about the alienation. These characteristics can be considered as follows [35];

- Alienation is related to alienation of an individual or something from an individual and something,
- Alienation is something exists in nature of human,
- Alienation was produced in early lives,
- Alienation is in close relationship with social environments of the individuals,
- Alienation is controlled by the powers between the individuals and their surrounding environments,

- In alienation, different human relations exist such as more competition, mutual disobedience, and aggressiveness.

Melvin Seeman, in his work "On The Meaning of Alienation" initiating several studies in sociology and psychology about the concept of *alienation* [36], separated the concept of alienation into five dimensions. These are; *weakness, meaninglessness, normlessness, isolation and moving away from himself* [37].

The first dimension of alienation, the *concept of weakness*, is sourced by alienation theory of Marks. According to this theory, weakness is the feelings created in an individual by the inconsistency between the actual and desired control level of expectations of an individual [37]. According to Hoy (1983), the feeling of alienation is significantly affected by external factors like chance, destiny and directed behaviors of others; it is the belief that the behaviors of an individual had little impacts on resultant outcomes and personal control was highly limited. In other words, the individual believes that entire conditions of the work life were controlled by the others and consequently he experienced these feelings [38].

The second dimension of alienation, *meaninglessness dimension*, is the state in which the individual doesn't know what to believe or which realities to believe. The individual in this dimension doesn't know what to select among the choices presented to him [37].

The third dimension of alienation, *normlessness dimension*, was resulted from anonymous concept of Durheim. Normlessness exists in cases in which the social rules/norms regulating the life of an individual lost the validity as behavioral rules and the commonly adopted standards disappeared. In this dimension, alienated individual exhibits behaviors not adopted by the society to reach the socially accepted goals [37].

Isolation dimension is mostly mentioned in a case where the individual is isolated from the society and feels the rejected by the society. Therefore, the individual is not able to get into meaningful relations and contacts with the others. Alienated individual perceives himself as an "isolated island" without any contact and relations with his friends and co-workers. Such a case indicates that the individual accepted the concept of isolation. If the individual thinks that his interests are weak, finds his life meaningless, perceives himself as an individual who is not able to do anything and finds difficult to answer the question of "who am I?", then it can be stated that isolation and alienation has already started [35].

The last dimension of alienation, *moving away from oneself*, is the alienation of an individual to his ego. This dimension is resulted from an in-compliance between the behaviors and future expectations of an individual and as a result of different behaviors of the individual out of his expectations [37].

The above mentioned alienation dimensions of Seeman are widely accepted and supported in literature and empirical studies about the alienation concept. Thus, these dimensions conceptualized by Seeman will be used in the present study.

C. Personality Characteristics and Five-Factor Personality Model

Most of the psychologists and behavioral scientists envisage the concept of personality as a concept covering the personal characteristics of individuals, the relationships among these characteristics, and the ways of compliance with the other people or cases [39]. There isn't any single definition of personality over which psychologists are agreed upon [40]. Personality is defined in general as "consistent behavioral patterns resulted from the individual himself and inter-personality processes" [41]. The origin of the word comes from the Latin word "*persona*" [40].

Allport indicated that more than fifty different definitions could be used to express the coverage of personality concept by using the perspectives of various disciplines of the science [42]. Allport investigated the personality in two dimensions as of bio-social and bio-physical. While the individual is taken as the social stimulant in bio-social definition, the characteristics coming from the nature of human and the relationships with surroundings are considered in bio-physical definition [43].

According to psychologists, personality is the whole of self-specific and distinctive behaviors of an individual [44]. Hogan and Roberts (1996) interpreted the personality as the factors used to express the behaviors of individuals [45]. According to Funder (1997), personality the total of characteristics of the individual related to his thoughts, behaviors and feelings [46]. Personality in the broadest sense covers the following characteristics [47];

- It is composed of whole inherent and later acquired tendencies.
- It is the arrangement of these acquired tendencies.
- There are some differences separating the personal characteristics of an individual from the others.
- It adapts the tendencies of the individuals to surrounding environment.

Although there are several definitions made for personality, a distinctive theory has not put forward yet. Such a case may result from the different reflections of inherent and later acquired characteristics over each individual. The five-factor personality model, developed by Paul Costa and Robert McCrae in 1985, is a model gathering the entire personality characteristics in itself and explaining these characteristics in detail [48].

This model can be considered as a new perspective with an old history. Contrary to previous perspectives, it depends on scientific observations not on a theory and handles personality under five basic dimensions. Rather than categorizing the humans, it places them into different levels at various personality levels [49]. Paunonen et al. (1992) carried out a study in Canada, Finland, Poland and Germany and indicated that the model was not limited only with the English language and obtained results supporting the model. Model's validity was also proved largely in studies made in Dutch, German, Italian, Slovak, Hebrew, Hungarian, Chinese, Pilipino, Polish and Russian languages [50], [51]. According to Atkinson et al. (2006), discovery and validity of the model is a significant

progress in personality psychology. The reasons for common adaptation and widespread use of five-factor personality model in personality-related researches are: (a) the model is longitudinal and based on empirical studies, (b) measured characteristics keeps their continuity in time, (c) it has some biologic grounds, (d) it has been proved for different cultures and groups and (e) it is easy to assess and use psychometrically [52]. Basic dimensions of this model are as follows;

- **Extroversion:** The individuals in this dimension have characteristics of being assertive, initiative, social, energetic and talkative. Extrovert individuals communicate with the individuals of the group easily and the leads in finding and using the resources. They are open to outer world [40].
- **Neuroticism:** According to Costa and McCrae (1992), this factor expresses the lack of positive psychological competence and emotional balance [25]. The individuals in this dimension may have high temper, sadness, anger, instability and anxiety [53].
- **Competence:** The individuals in this dimension behaves friendly, likes working together, they are kind, gentle, softhearted, reassuring and highly tolerant individuals [54]. Compared to other people, they prefer working together rather than working in competition or struggle, they are flexible easy-going individuals [42].
- **Responsibility:** The personality characteristics of this dimension are being competent, steady, and aware of responsibilities, success-oriented, self-disciplined and cautious. Responsible individuals are effective, organized and non-delinquent individuals [55].
- **Openness (Open for Experiences):** The individuals of this dimension are sensitive, flexible, curious, intellectual, intelligent, adventurous individuals. They are open to experiences and have high imagination [56], [57].

The five-factor personality characteristics of McCrea and Costa in different dimensions can be summarized in a table as follows;

TABLE II
 PERSONALITY CHARACTERISTICS [25]

Extroversion	Neuroticism	Competence	Responsibility	Openness
Initiative	Anxious	Reliable	Self-disciplined	Fantastic
Active	Have hostile feelings	Honest	Having sense of mission	Esthetic
Assertive	Depressive	Thinking others sometimes before himself	Talented	Emotional
Excitement-oriented	Aware of himself	Competent	Stable	Active
Optimistic	Mindless	Humble	Cautious	Have ideas
Warm blooded	Fragile	Tender minded	Struggle for the success	Have values

Today, five-factor personality model is the most widely accepted model worldwide. Despite such a wide acceptance, this system is totally definitive but not explanatory [54].

III. METHODOLOGY OF STUDY AND RESULTS

The basic objective of this research was to investigate the role of psychological harassment behaviors and personality characteristics over work alienation. The research universe was composed of the staff of Provincial Special Administration. For the research sample, survey forms were distributed 350 employees of the organization. Of these forms, 210 responses were taken and 204 of them were taken into consideration for assessments because of various reasons.

A four-section survey was prepared to measure the variables of the research and to reach the goals of the research. The first section of the survey was composed of questions acquiring the demographic characteristics of the participants. The second section was composed of mobbing, the third section was composed of work alienation and the last section was composed of five-factor personality dimensions scales. To A 33-item "Psychological Violence Behaviors at Work Place" scale developed by Yildirim and Yildirim [58] was used to measure the psychological harassment behaviors (mobbing) to which employees are exposed. This scale is considered under four main headings: Isolation of the individuals from the work, assault to professional status, assault to personality and direct negative behaviors. To find out the frequency of behaviors, 5-point likert method was used in which 1 indicating "never" and 5 indicating "always". To measure work alienation, 3-factor work alienation scale of Mottaz (1981) was used. This scale was translated into Turkish by Uysaler (2010), [59] in a thesis and relevant statistical analyses were performed. The sub-dimensions of the scale are; Weakening, become meaningless and self-alienation. To measure the personality characteristics of the participants, "Five-factor Personality" scale developed by John, Donahue and Kentle (1991) and translated by Tekin (2012), [25] was used. This scale was composed 44 questions and 5 sub-dimensions. These sub-dimensions are; a- Neuroticism, b- extroversion, c-competence, d-responsibility and e- openness. The questions of work alienation and five-factor personality characteristics were assessed by 5-point likert method was used in which 1 indicating "totally disagree" and 5 indicating "totally agree".

Survey data were evaluated statistically by using SPSS 20.0 software. Initially reliability analysis was performed, and then correlation and regression analyses were used. Resultant outcomes were discussed with the previous literatures.

A. Research Hypotheses

The research hypotheses were formed as follows:

H₁: There is a positive significant relationship between psychological harassment and work alienation.

H₂: Five-factor personality characteristics model has significant impacts on psychological harassment.

H₃: Five-factor personality characteristics model has significant impacts on work alienation,

H₄: The dimensions of psychological harassment behaviors are significant in explaining work alienation variable.

H₅: Five-factor personality characteristics are significant in explaining work alienation variable.

B. Results

1) Results about Demographic Characteristics

Of the research participants (204 employees) 84,8% was male and 15,2% was female. With regard to age of the participants, 20% was between 25-35 years of age, 13,2% was between 36-40 years, 41,7% was between 41-50 years and 24% was over the age of 50. The participants were mainly high-school graduates (40,7%). Also, 18,1% had primary school, 11,8% had vocational collage, 16,7% had undergraduate and 12,7% had graduate level education. With regard to years of experience in the organization, 50% of the participants had an experience of over 10 years. Similarly, with regard to professional seniority, majority (59,8%) of the participants had professional seniority of over 10 years.

The participants were asked whether or not they have ever been exposed to psychological harassment behaviors. Of the participants, 13% replied as yes, 71% replied as no and 17% replied as not sure. The exposure ratio for psychological harassment behaviors was 16% in Europe and the USA. Such a ratio in Turkey is about 30-35% [49]. The ratio of psychological harassment behaviors of the present study is below the Turkish averages.

2) Reliability Analysis of Research Variables, Averages and Standard Deviations

The scales used in this study were separated for each dimension and reliability of each dimension was tested by calculating the Cronbach Alpha value and average and standard deviations are provided in the following Table. Cronbach Alfa (α) values were calculated as 0,941 for psychological intimidation scale, 0,791 for work alienation scale and 0,880 for five-factor personality characteristics scale. Such results indicated that the scales were highly reliable ($\alpha > 0,70$).

TABLE III
CRONBACH'S ALPHA, AVERAGE AND STANDARD DEVIATION VALUES

Dimensions	Cronbach's Alpha	Average	Standard deviation
Psychological Harassment	0,941	1,95	0,648
Isolation of Individual from the work	0,811	2,13	0,683
Assault to professional status	0,866	2,08	0,764
Assault to personality	0,897	1,73	0,739
Direct Negative Behaviors	0,931	1,70	1,042
Work Alienation	0,791	3,06	0,545
Weakness	0,761	2,78	0,670
Meaningless	0,755	3,19	0,764
Self-alienation	0,702	3,20	0,725
Five-factor Personality Characteristics	0,880	3,18	0,482
Neuroticism	0,810	3,05	0,561
Competence	0,756	3,13	0,531
Extroversion	0,689	3,15	0,625
Responsibility	0,794	3,29	0,598
Openness	0,825	3,26	0,577

The table indicates the psychological harassment exposure ratio of the participants as 1,95. Such a ratio corresponds to

“rarely” response in scale questions. In other words, participants indicated that they were rarely exposed to psychological harassment behaviors. Among the sub-dimensions of the psychological harassment scale, isolation of the individual from the work had an average of 2,13; assault to professional status had an average of 2,08; assault to personality had an average of 1,73 and direct negative behaviors had an average ratio of 1,70. While the highest average was observed in isolation of the individual from the work, the lowest average was seen in direct negative behaviors. Such results revealed that participants mostly exposed to isolation behaviors such as ignorance at work place, not to take response to talking desires, interruptions while talking, not to inform about important issues, criticism, pressure made along work release and etc. They were less exposed to negative behaviors like physical violence, damaging their possessions, leaving the atmosphere he existed in and etc.

The average of the responses given questions about work alienation was calculated as 3,06. The participants mostly replied as neither agree nor disagree. In other words, work alienation cases were at medium levels. With regard to sub-dimensions, weakness had the lowest average (0,78). The average of meaningless dimension was calculated as 3,19 and average of self-alienation dimension was calculated as 3,20.

According to Table, five-factor personality characteristics had an average of 3,18. With regard to sub-dimensions of this variable, neuroticism had an average of 3,05; competence had 3,13; extroversion had 3,15; responsibility had 3,29 and openness dimension had an average of 3,26.

3) Data Analysis

The existence of linear relationships between the independent variables of the research **Psychological Harassment Scale: Isolation of the Individual from Work, Assault to Professional Status, Assault to Personality, Direct Negative Behaviors** and **Five-factor Personality Characteristics: Neuroticism, Competence, Extroversion, Responsibility, Openness** and **Work Alienation** were investigated through scatter diagram of SPSS software. Results revealed a linear relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable; Pearson correlation coefficients among the variables were calculated and then stepwise regression analysis was applied and results were explained. Significance level was considered as 0.05.

In this study, initially the relationships between the dependent variable (work alienation) and the independent variables (psychological harassment and personality characteristics) were presents (Table IV); then the results of stepwise regression analysis performed over the variables taken as explanatories of work alienation were provided in Table V.

4) Relationships among Research Variables

The results of correlation analysis performed to measure the level of relationship between the dependent and the

independent variables were summarized in table provided below.

TABLE IV
CORRELATION ANALYSIS

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
1.Work Alienation	1											
2.Isolation of the Individual from Work	-0,07	1										
3.Assults to Professional Status	-0,06	0,55	1									
4.Assult to Personality	0,05	0,55	0,54	1								
5.Direct Negative Behaviors	0,26	0,49	0,39	0,76	1							
6.Neurocitism	0,31	0,03	0,18	0,17	0,16	1						
7.Extroversion	0,20	-0,11	0,01	-0,14	-0,09	0,62	1					
8.Competence	0,28	-0,07	0,06	-0,05	0,00	0,56	0,62	1				
9.Responsibility	0,26	-0,07	0,04	-0,10	-0,09	0,52	0,59	0,71	1			
10.Openness	0,37	-0,14	-0,07	-0,06	0,01	0,65	0,64	0,64	0,63	1		
11.Psychological Harassment	0,03	0,77	0,70	0,78	0,72	0,08	-0,12	-0,05	-0,08	-0,19	1	
12.Personality	0,34	-0,09	0,04	-0,05	-0,01	0,79	0,83	0,84	0,84	0,86	-0,09	1

Correlation is significant at 0.05 level.

The results in table revealed that there was a *negative* but weak relationship between isolation of the individual from the work ($r = -0,07$, $p < 0,05$) and assault to professional status ($r = -0,06$, $p < 0,05$) dimensions and work alienation. There was a *positive significant relationship* between the other dimensions of psychological harassment, assault to personality ($r = 0,05$, $p < 0,05$) and direct negative behaviors ($r = 0,26$, $p < 0,05$) dimensions and work alienation. Also, a *positive significant relationship* was observed between the general psychological harassment and work alienation at 0.03 level.

Positive significant relationships of work alienation were also observed with five-factor personality characteristics dimensions of neuroticism ($r = 0,31$, $p < 0,05$), extroversion ($r = 0,20$, $p < 0,05$), competence ($r = 0,28$, $p < 0,05$), responsibility ($r = 0,26$, $p < 0,05$) and openness ($r = 0,37$, $p < 0,05$). *Positive significant but weak relationships* were also observed between general of five-factor personality characteristic and work alienation at 0.34 level.

Among the personality characteristics of the individuals exposed to psychological harassment behaviors, there was 0,08 *positive relationship* between neuroticism dimension and psychological harassment dimension, -0,12 *negative relationship* between extroversion and psychological harassment, -0,05 *negative relationship* between competence and psychological harassment, -0,08 *negative relationship*

between responsibility and psychological harassment, -0,19 *negative relationship* between openness and psychological harassment.

5) Results of Step-Wise Regression Analysis Performed over Five-factor Personality Characteristics and Psychological Harassment Sub-Dimensions

ANOVA table of step-wise regression analysis revealed the significance of explained variation or regression model. As it can be seen in Table V, since the step-wise regression analysis did not significantly explain work alienation, the psychological harassment sub-dimensions of; *Isolation of the Individual from the Work, Assault to Professional Status, Five-factor Personality Characteristics* sub-dimensions of; *Neuroticism, Extroversion, Competence, Responsibility, Psychological Harassment and Personality* variables were not included into analysis; the other three variables were processes in step-wise regression analysis. Both the standardized regression coefficients and dual and relative correlations revealed positive significant relationships between *Openness, Direct Negative Behaviors and Assault to Personality* and work alienation. The variables of *Openness, Direct Negative Behaviors and Assault to Personality* was able to explain about 24% of total variation related to work alienation variable ($R = 0,490$, $R^2 = 0,240$, $p < 0,001$).

TABLE V
RESULTS OF STEP-WISE REGRESSION ANALYSIS

Model		Non-standardized coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Relative Correlations		R	R ²
		B	Std. Dev.	Beta					
1	Constant	1,918	0,205		9,372				
	Openness	1,918	0,205		5,654	0,370	0,370	0,370	0,137
2	Constant	1,918	0,062	0,370	8,302				
	Openness	1,698	0,204		5,846	0,370	0,381	0,450	0,202
	Direct Negative Behaviors	0,348	0,060	0,368	4,063	0,258	0,276		
	Constant	0,126	0,031	0,256	9,038				
3	Openness	1,901	0,210		5,606	0,369	0,346		
	Direct Negative Behaviors	0,328	0,059	0,348	5,082	0,338	0,313	0,490	0,240
	Assault to Personality	0,239	0,047	0,484	-3,141	-0,217	-0,194		

The dependent variable is work alienation, $p < 0,001$

Standardized regression coefficient (Beta) in explanation of work alienation by "Openness" variable taken into consideration at the first step of step-wise regression analysis was found to be as 0,205. It indicates that "Openness" variable alone was able to explain 13% variations in work alienations ($R^2=0.137$).

Beside the variable "Openness", the variable "Direct Negative Behaviors" was also introduced into the second step of step-wise regression analysis. The variables "Openness" and "Direct Negative Behaviors" together were able to explain about 20% of academic success ($R= 0, 450, R^2 = 0,202$). Keeping the other variables constant, "Openness" variable had a Beta coefficient of 0,204; "Direct Negative Behaviors" had a Beta coefficient of 0,060. The t-values of both Beta coefficients were found to be significant (respectively as $t= 5,846, t= 4,063, p<0,001$).

Beside the variables "Openness" and "Direct Negative Behaviors", the variable "Assault to Personality" was introduced into the third step of step-wise regression analysis.

The variables all three together were able to explain 24% of academic success ($R= 0,490, R^2 = 0.240$).

Keeping the other variables constant, "Openness" variable had a Beta coefficient of 0,256; "Direct Negative Behaviors" had a Beta coefficient of 0,348; "Assault to Personality" variable had a Beta coefficient of 0,484. The t-values of all three variables were found to be significant ($p < 0.001$).

Considering both regression coefficients related to variables "Openness", "Direct Negative Behaviors" and "Assault to Personality" and R^2 and t values of these variables, it was observed that work alienation of employees was significantly explained firstly by "Openness", secondly by "Direct Negative Behavior" and thirdly by "Assault to Personality". On the other hand, it was observed that the variables of Isolation of the Individual from the Work, Assault to Professional Status, Neuroticism, Extroversion, Competence, Responsibility, Psychological Harassment and Personality did not have significant effects on work alienation of employees.

Conceptual model was then created as follows;

Fig. 1 Conceptual Model (together with Correlation and Regression Values)

IV. CONCLUSION

The present study, investigating the role of psychological harassment behaviors and personality characteristics over the work alienation, revealed significant results. The research universe was composed of the staff of Provincial Special Administration. While the surveys were limited with psychological harassment, work alienation and five-factor personality characteristics, the research sample was limited with employees of Provincial Special Administration. Correlation and step-wise regression analyses were performed to analyze the separate and overall effects of sub-dimensions of psychological harassment and personality characteristics on work alienation. Correlation analysis revealed weak significant relationships between psychological harassment

behaviors and personality characteristics and work alienation. Therefore, the hypotheses of; "**H₁**: There is a positive significant relationship between psychological harassment and work alienation, **H₂**: Five-factor personality characteristics model has significant impacts on psychological harassment, **H₃**: Five-factor personality characteristics model has significant impacts on work alienation" were accepted.

Step-wise regression analysis revealed significant relationships and roles of psychological harassment behaviors sub-dimensions of assault to personality, direct negative behaviors and personality characteristics of openness on work alienation. Each variable was introduced into the model one by one to see the effects of significant variables and their general explanation capacities were evaluated. While the explanation ratio of the first model was 13%, the last model

including three variables had an explanation ratio of 24%. According to these results;

H₄: *The dimensions of psychological harassment behaviors are significant in explaining work alienation variable.*

Since the explanation of direct negative behaviors and assault to personality dimensions of work alienation was significant, the hypothesis **H₄** was accepted with regard to these dimensions.

H₅: *Five-factor personality characteristics are significant in explaining work alienation variable.*

Since the explanation of openness dimension of work alienation variable was also significant, the hypothesis **H₅** was also accepted for these dimensions.

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